

OPTIMIZING PREGRAVIDARNOY PODGOTOVKI GINSCHIN WITH CHRONIC HYPOPLASTIC ENDOMETRITOM

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Relevance: One of the global problems of modern reproductive medicine, far from a final solution, according to researchers, is the disruption of implantation processes due to a defect in the morphological substrate and / or dysfunction of the endometrial interface [2, 3, 5, 6] . This seems particularly important in terms of predicting the outcome of pregnancy during in vitro fertilization (IVF), a still elusive goal of reproductive science, which has determined the active search for prognostic markers [5].

Purpose of the study: A systematic review and meta-analysis showed that in ART protocols, there is a significant delay in endometrial thickness (ET) from the lower normal limit, with a significant delay in the middle and end of the follicular phase of the stimulated cycle. observed. the probability of successful implantation, which is one of the reasons for the phenomenon of repeated reproductive failure (RIF - repeated implantation failure) [7, 8]. In this context, maternal age, ovarian reserve, and endometrial receptivity (ER) markers have previously been evaluated. Of course, RE is an integral part of implantation, so determining the exact marker of implantation is very useful in ART cycles.

Research materials: Despite many studies in the field of uterine implantology and embryology, today there is no ideal sign of EC. The lack of diagnostic accuracy, prognostic value and invasive nature of EC histological and biochemical markers limit their clinical application [5].

Observed results: Endometrium is a specific tissue of the body that undergoes regular dynamic changes every month in women of reproductive age: transformation, repair and regeneration processes [4]. All these changes are primarily aimed at preparing for embryo implantation. Changes in the endometrium that occur during the menstrual cycle reflect the cumulative effects of ovarian cycle steroids. The functional layer of the endometrium begins to grow under the influence of estrogen (Es), it begins to grow until it reaches its maximum level at the beginning of the peak release of luteinizing hormone (LH), and the preovulatory and

postovulatory growth of progesterone (Pr) is responsible. for the secretory transformation of the endometrium, which is accompanied by structural changes in the endometrial pattern [9].

Conclusion: It should be noted that, due to its non-invasiveness and universal availability, transvaginal sonography is the most widely used and very informative method of ER assessment in ART protocols. In dynamics, during the sonographic study, an increase in TE in the follicular phase and its transformation from a hypoechoic line to a three-layer compact form of a hyperechoic pattern in the postovulatory period can be observed. It is believed that the presence of a three-layer structure of the endometrium on the day of ovulation induction is associated with an increase in the probability of pregnancy [10].

In transvaginal sonography, TE is measured as the maximum distance between the echogenic interfaces of the myometrium and the endometrium in a plane drawn along the central longitudinal axis of the uterine body. Today, ART protocols have proven $TE < 7$ mm in the absence of endometrial pattern formation at the time of embryo transfer.

Regarding the sonographic assessment of structure and ER, the appearance of a three-layered endometrial line on the day of the ovulation trigger (three-layered) is defined as class A or receptive (receptive), while a homogeneous phenotypic appearance, or multiple layered endometrium, classified as class C - non-receptive (immune).

The secretion of progesterone (Pr) initiates changes in the endometrium, which is reflected in the homogeneity of the connecting uterine zone and the clarity of the central echogenic line in this anatomical pattern defined as class B [11].

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